

ON THE DECREASE IN STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBRE-EPOXY WITH SIZE

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ABSTRACT

Four point bending, pin-ended buckling and short beam shear tests have been carried out on scaled specimens of unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy. A significant reduction in tensile and compressive strain at failure and interlaminar shear strength was found with increasing specimen size, showing that none of these values can be regarded strictly as material properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Strengths measured with small coupons are often considered to be material constants, and used to design large composite structures. However, in practice there is a tendency for the strength of fibre reinforced composites to decrease with increasing specimen size. This has been documented for tensile strength of glass fibre [e.g. 1] and carbon fibre composites [e.g. 2], but there are still questions as to the magnitude of the size effect. Possible similar effects in other failure modes are less well understood.

The present paper summarises results of scaled tests carried out at Bristol University to investigate the magnitude of size effects for different failure modes in unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy. Four point bending tests were used to produce tensile failure [3], pin ended buckling tests to give compressive failure [4], and three point short beam bending tests to produce shear failure [5].

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Four-point bending tests

Three series of tests were carried out, with all linear dimensions scaled up by a factor of two between each series. A stiff steel fixture was used with fixed loading and support noses. In order to try to avoid failures at the point of loading whilst keeping the specimen reasonably short, the distance between the central loading noses was fixed at one sixth of the distance between the outer support noses. The dimensions for the smallest specimens are shown in Figure 1. Small pads of 1mm thick fabric reinforced rubber were greased and placed underneath the loading noses in order to distribute loads into the specimens and avoid local failures. Thicker sheets of the same

Figure 1. Dimensions for four-point bending tests on small specimens (mm)

rubber were not available and so two or four thicknesses of rubber were used for the larger specimens. The width of the support and loading noses was kept constant, but it was not thought that this would have any significant effect.

All specimens were cut with a diamond wheel from plates of unidirectional 913/XAS carbon fibre-epoxy of 60% nominal volume fraction supplied by Westland Helicopters. 25, 50 and 100 plies were used, giving nominal thicknesses of 3.175, 6.35 and 12.7mm. The actual thicknesses were close to these values except for the third plate, where the average thickness was about 13.3 mm.

Strain gauges with 2mm gauge length were attached to the centre of each specimen on the tension side. They were then loaded in an Avery Denison test machine under load control. Load was applied very slowly, each test taking approximately ten minutes. The strain was monitored and the maximum value at failure recorded.

2.2. Buckling Tests

In order to consistently obtain compressive failures, a material with a higher ratio of tensile to compressive strength than XAS/913 was necessary, and so unidirectional T800/924 carbon fibre-epoxy was used for these tests.

Compressive failures in four point flexural tests tend to occur near the loading rollers where there are stress concentrations and stress components other than in the fibre direction as a result of the local contact. For this reason a pin-ended buckling rig was developed which also produces flexural failure, but without any stress concentrations in the region where failure is expected to occur. Since the specimen is end loaded, there is also a net compressive stress on the specimen, although this is relatively small compared with the bending stress. At the centre of the specimen there is no shear. Moving away from the centre there are shear stresses, but these are small away from the ends provided that the specimen is reasonably long.

Two series of tests were carried out, with all dimensions scaled by a factor of four. Specimens were compressed between two fixtures with semi-circular rollers to permit rotation of the ends. To allow smooth rotation the rollers were made with a slightly smaller radius than the seats in which they fitted and PTFE tape was laid between the two surfaces. The specimens were located in slots in the rollers which were designed to be a tight fit. To facilitate

Figure 2. Dimensions for buckling tests on small specimens (mm)

bending of the specimens the slots were positioned eccentrically such that in the unloaded position one surface of the specimen lay along the centre line of the rig.

The smaller specimens were 50 mm long and 10 mm wide with 16 plies. The nominal thickness was 2 mm, although actual measured values were slightly higher, with a mean of 2.16 mm. Strain gauges 1 mm long were attached at the centre of both sides of the specimens. Dimensions for the rig with the smaller specimens are shown in Figure 2. For the tests on the larger specimens all dimensions on the test pieces and rig were exactly scaled except for the width of the rollers and seats, which for practical reasons was only doubled. This was not thought likely to have any significant effect although it would increase the contact pressure between the rollers and seats and might make sticking more likely.

Tests were carried out in an Avery Denison machine under load control. Earlier work had showed a tendency for specimens to delaminate from the ends if loaded too quickly and so the tests were performed very slowly, over a period of 15 to 20 minutes. Loads and strains as a function of time were recorded by a computer data logging system.

2.3. Three point bending tests

Short beam bending tests were carried out on specimens cut from the same 100 ply unidirectional XAS/913 plate as used for the four point bending tests. For shear failure where the resin properties are crucial, it was thought that differences due to fabrication such as different curing in different thickness panels could be important. By using the same panel for all specimens, such differences are excluded.

Table 1. Size effect for tensile failure in four point bending

Specimen Thickness	Mean Tensile Strain (%)	Coefficient of Variation	Number of Specimens
25 plies	1.85	3.1%	7
50 plies	1.70	1.9%	9
100 plies	1.58	-	1

The smallest specimens were 12.5 mm long, 5 mm wide and 1.6 mm thick. A span of 8 mm was used, giving a span to thickness ratio of 5. The other specimens had all dimensions scaled by factors of 2, 4 and 8. Specimens were cut using a diamond wheel except for the surfaces of the thickest specimens which were skimmed on a surface grinder.

Fixed loading and support noses were used. In order to avoid compressive damage at the points of contact, larger diameters were employed than in the standard tests. For the smallest specimens the loading nose was 10 mm diameter and the support noses were 5 mm diameter. These sizes were scaled for the larger specimens. With these diameters it was not necessary to use rubber at the points of contact.

Specimens were tested in an Instron servo-hydraulic test machine under displacement control. For the smallest specimens a loading rate of 0.5 mm/min was used, and this was increased proportionately for the larger specimens.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Four point bending tests

Most of the smaller specimens failed in tension with a brush like appearance. Failure occurred gradually with fibre bundles failing and splitting off at the surface first, and then progressively through the thickness. Average values of the maximum surface strains at failure are shown in Table 1. These are in fact the strains at which the gauges broke, but since this normally occurred when a large number of fibres had failed, it is a reasonable estimate of the ultimate failure strain.

Some of the smaller specimens and all but one of the larger ones behaved differently. Initially some bundles failed in tension, and then there was a sudden, catastrophic compression failure, in most cases initiating near one of the loading rollers. The tensile strains at which this occurred are shown in Table 2. Figure 3 compares results for tensile and compressive failures.

Table 2. Size effect for compressive failure in four point bending

Specimen Thickness	Mean Tensile Strain (%)	Coefficient of Variation	Number of Specimens
25 plies	1.80	6.5%	3
50 plies	1.62	3.7%	3
100 plies	1.35	10.9%	5

Figure 3. Size effect in four-point bending

3.2. Buckling tests

All specimens failed suddenly in compression. For the smaller specimens, the fractures propagated across the width at an angle of about 73° to the fibre direction. In all cases one end of the fracture was within 5% of the specimen length on either side of the centre. The large specimens behaved very similarly, although they showed more variability in the angle and location of the fracture. Two of the failures initiated about 10% and 20% of the specimen length from the centre. These cases also gave the lowest strains at failure.

Table 3 shows the results in terms of the mean values of compressive strain at the centre of the specimens at failure. These are not exactly the true strains at failure because there is some variation in bending moment and hence in strain along the specimen. However, because of the shape the specimens take up under load, the bending moment is reasonably constant in the central region. Since most specimens failed quite close to the centre, the actual failure strains will be close to the values measured. If anything, the true magnitude of the size effect will be slightly greater than that shown in Table 3 since the larger specimens tended to fail further from the centre where the actual strains were lower.

Table 3. Size effect for compressive failure in buckling

Specimen Thickness	Mean Compressive Strain (%)	Coefficient of Variation	Number of Specimens
16 plies	1.62	7.8%	9
64 plies	1.24	12.2%	5

Table 4. Size effect for interlaminar shear strength

Specimen Thickness	Mean Shear Stress (MPa)	Coefficient of Variation	Number of Specimens
1.6 mm	93.8	1.5%	6
3.2 mm	91.0	3.7%	9
6.4 mm	86.1	12.3%	6
12.8 mm	69.5	8.2%	5

3.3. Short beam shear tests

All specimens failed suddenly with a sharp drop in load. The maximum load P was used together with the measured specimen thickness t and width b to calculate the apparent interlaminar shear strength τ :

$$\tau = 3P/4bt \tag{1}$$

Table 4 gives the mean values of interlaminar shear strength. These are plotted in Figure 4, with the bars showing the full range of results.

In most cases there was a single dominant shear crack located somewhere between 40% and 80% of the way through the thickness from the top surface where the loading roller contacted. No damage was seen under the rollers.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Tensile failure

Results are very consistent, with coefficients of variation of only 2 to 3%. Comparison of the 25 and 50 ply specimens shows a reduction of tensile strain to failure of 8% for a doubling of specimen dimensions. Although there is only one result for the 100 ply specimens, it also shows a similar reduction.

There is clearly a significant size effect on tensile strength, and no indication of any diminishing of the effect even at these moderately sized

Figure 4. Size effect on short beam shear strength

specimens. If the tests are interpreted in terms of Weibull strength theory, the size effect indicates a Weibull modulus of about 25, consistent with values reported elsewhere for tensile failure. However, Weibull theory is based on catastrophic failure initiating at the worst defect. The low coefficients of variation and gradual, non-catastrophic failure mode suggest that Weibull theory is not really appropriate for unidirectional composites which fail in a brush-like mode in tension [6].

4.2. Compressive failure

The four point bending results for those specimens failing in compression show a reduction of 25% in strain at failure for an increase in dimensions of a factor of four. There are relatively few of the smaller specimens, and failure may have been influenced by the stress concentrations at the rollers, and so the buckling test results give a more reliable indication of the size effect. These show a 23% reduction in compressive strain at failure for a factor of four increase in specimen size. Although this is a different type of carbon fibre-epoxy, the magnitude of the size effect is very similar to that from the four point bending tests.

For both types of specimen, there is much more variation in strains than for the tension tests. Also failure was catastrophic, and so Weibull strength theory may be more applicable to compressive failure than to failure in tension. The magnitude of the size effect implies a Weibull modulus of about 15, significantly lower than that in tension. In contrast to the tensile results, for compressive failure there is reasonable agreement between the measured variability of strains and that expected on the basis of the Weibull modulus.

Both of these sets of results show a larger size effect in compression than that found in tension. This explains the change in failure mode for the four point bending specimens from normally tensile at small specimen size to normally compressive for the largest specimens.

4.3. Interlaminar shear failure

There is a significant size effect for interlaminar shear strength, with a 26% reduction in strength between the smallest and largest specimens. However, it appears that the magnitude of the effect diminishes with reducing specimen size. There is a reduction in strength of 19% between the second largest and largest sizes, whilst the reduction is only 3% from the smallest to the next largest size. It appears that as the specimen size decreases, an upper limit on strength is approached. This is also supported by the fact that the highest strengths achieved are very similar for the smallest three sets of specimens, whilst the lowest strengths change considerably. As a result the coefficient of variation tends to reduce with specimen size.

A possible explanation for these observations is that the strength of the large specimens is controlled by defects, but as the size is reduced the probability of finding a significant defect becomes small. For small specimens the strength therefore tends to approach the shear strength of the material in the absence of defects.

4.4. Strength as a material property

Significant reductions of strength with increasing specimen size have been shown to occur for tensile, compressive and interlaminar shear failure of

unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy. It has also been shown elsewhere that if the stress is not constant, the magnitude of the stress gradient can be expected to have a significant effect on strength in both tension [7] and compression [8]. These results cast serious doubt on the notion of strength being an intrinsic material property with a constant value. Research on delamination of glass fibre-epoxy has also shown that the mode II fracture energy is not constant, but varies significantly with specimen size [9].

5. CONCLUSIONS

There is a significant size effect for tensile, compressive and interlaminar shear failure in unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy. For a factor of four increase in all linear dimensions, a reduction in strain at failure of 16% in tension and 23% in compression was found. The interlaminar shear strength was reduced by 26% for an increase in dimensions of a factor of 8. None of these values can therefore be regarded strictly as material properties. This shows the need for caution in determining design allowables for large composite structures from small coupon tests.

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